

Script for the focused interview

Project: "Applicability of open science practices to completed research projects"

Very nice that you agreed to be interviewed. Thank you very much in advance.

- As previously mentioned in the email, I would like to record the interview with your consent. Do you have any questions on this? If not, I would start the recording now.

[Start recording]

I would suggest that before we get started,

- I just briefly introduce the interview structure,
- and then we clarify questions,
- and then we jump into the interview.

Unless of course you would like to clarify questions right now.

In the project, I'm interested in different perspectives on what open science means in the research practice. That's what I want to talk about today, I'm interested in your perspective on open science. open science is a very heterogeneous concept. For example, scientists come from different research traditions, have different research interests, or use different research methods. Accordingly, what it means to do open science differs between scientists and between research projects.

In the interview, I am interested in your perspective on the implementation of aspects of open science. More specifically, what aspects of open science you consider to be relevant in the process of one of your research projects and how these would be implemented in research projects as an example.

Since I am interested in open science across the project span, it would certainly be helpful if you think of a past research project of yours. From that project, I would be interested in what aspects of open science you find to be relevant. I am less interested in what aspects you have actually implemented, but more in what you consider possible and useful in principle. I think a subject-specific project is particularly appropriate here, as opposed to meta-science. Before we get started and I ask you the exact question, is there anything unclear to you so far? Is there anything you would like to clarify?

[Narrative prompt:]

Please recall one of your most recently completed research projects. If you think about the entire project span, from the first idea to the completion of the project: Which aspects of open science do you consider to be relevant and how can they be exemplarily implemented in research projects?

[Exmanent follow-up questions:]

"Are there other aspects of open science that you consider to be relevant in your research projects (i.e., potentially others as well)? If so, how could these be implemented?"

[Immanent follow-up questions:]

"You talked about ... before. Can you make this aspect a little clearer with an example? How would the aspect be implemented?"

[END]

Then, in conclusion, I'd like to ask you: is there a question that I didn't ask? Or did I forget to ask something that would be important in your eyes?

Good. Then we have reached the end and I thank you very much!